

UNIVERSITY-INDUSTRY COOPERATION IN ENHANCING ENGINEERING EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

Emmanuel Akintunde Okunade

Dept. of Civil Engineering, University of Ado-Ekiti, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria, e-mail: eaokunade@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the benefits of University-Industry cooperation in terms of the role and contributions of industry in enhancing engineering education in Nigeria. Considered are the financial contributions of industry through direct and indirect means to engineering education, which includes provision of equipment and infrastructure, funding of research, and contributions to other engineering educational programmes. Industry's participation and contributions to the informal aspect of undergraduates' training outside the universities are also considered. Industry's contributions to the engineer's education even beyond the conventional university training to the time of attaining chartered status and throughout the professional life of the practicing engineer are also examined in detail. In conclusion, while the traditional research partnerships obtainable in the advanced economies may not be available in the university-industry relationship in Nigeria because of its low-technology-driven economy, it is found that many of the existing practices could find beneficial applicability in other countries.

KEYWORDS: education funding, industrial contribution

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, university-industry cooperation has been a symbiotic or mutually beneficial interactive relationship. It is widely believed that university-industry cooperation increases technological innovation and hence, economic development, and that this is responsible for an increase in recent times in the number of university-industry relationships and in the level of industry's financial support of academic research and development programmes (Wu, 2000). Several main reasons, which are claimed to motivate industry to increase university-industry cooperation, have been provided (Atlan, 1987; Peters *et al.*, 1982). They are: (i) access to manpower, including well-trained graduates and knowledgeable faculty; (ii) access to basic and applied research results from which new products and processes will evolve; (iii) solutions to specific problems or professional expertise, not usually found in an individual firm; (iv) access to university facilities, not available in the company; (v) assistance in continuing education and training; (vi) obtaining prestige or enhancing the company's image; and (vii) being good local citizens or fostering good community relations.

Notwithstanding the benefits motivating industry to make its contributions, the focus of this paper will be the benefits derived by the universities in the university-industry relationships, and the various contributions of industry towards the enhancement of engineering education in Nigeria.

On the other hand, the reasons for universities seeking cooperation with industry appear to be relatively simple. Several of these reasons have been identified (Peters *et al.*, 1982). They are: (i) Industry provides a new source of money for university; (ii) Industrial money involves less "red tape" than government money; (iii) Industrially sponsored research provides students with exposure to real world research problems; (iv) Industrially sponsored research provides university researchers a chance to work on intellectually challenging research programs; (v) Some government funds are available for applied research, based upon a joint effort between university and industry.

It is in the light of the above that the special contributions of industry with regard to the enhancement of engineering education in Nigeria will be considered. However, in view of the peculiarities of the

Nigerian situation as a developing country, these contributions do extend much beyond the scope already mentioned.

Historical Necessity of University-Industry Relationship in Nigeria

From a global perspective, economic and social developments are increasingly driven by the advancement and application of knowledge (Saint *et al*, 2004). In the current global economic order, the path of national development for any nation is to shift from a labor-intensive to a knowledge-intensive economy, and to enhance the level of technological sophistication. New technology is critical to the industrial corporations' competitiveness. Companies can develop their technical capabilities and products either based on internal research and development (R&D) or outsourcing. Although it remains necessary to build own internal R&D capacity, the external sources of technologies have become more and more important (Wu, 2000). To develop technologies externally can be conducted in several ways, including inter-firm cooperation, industry-research institution cooperation, and university-industry cooperation. Among them, the university-industry research cooperation (UIRC) has been considered a top issue by many scholars regarding the national competitiveness, and that industrial companies can benefit a lot if they are able to leverage the technical resources of universities (Wu, 2000).

The importance and role of the universities and research institutes in the growth of industry and the economy of Nigeria has been recognized for years. This was reflected in the National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1981), which provided that: "Government will support closer links between the universities, industry and the various research councils," and that "Government will encourage locally-based industries to develop direct links with research institutes and universities to facilitate research into their products and problems." With regards to this, the Policy further stipulated that "a greater proportion of educational expenditure will be devoted to science and technology."

However, funds provided by government seemed to be perpetually inadequate for the financial implementation of the policies and programmes earmarked for national development. There appears to be a perennial shortage of funds for the education system at all levels (UNESCO, 1998). An examination of the overall allocation of financial resources to education in recent times shows little discernible pattern beyond an ad hoc response to need. For example, when comparing the federal government allocations to education, health, agriculture and defence between the years 1968 and 1978, it was found that education came second to defence in the amount of money allocated to each sector each year. Thereafter, the picture changed and federal allocation to education continued to decline from 24.5% of the recurrent budget in 1978 to less than 8% in 1996 (UNESCO, 1998). Unfortunately, there had been nothing to reverse this trend since then.

All the foregoing is against the backdrop of the United Nation's prescription of setting aside a minimum of 26% of the annual budgetary allocation to education for meaningful national development. However, other sectors of the economy, namely agriculture, health, social services (electricity, water, roads, telecommunications, housing, etc.), security and defence, and others, equally demand priority attention. The scenario is one of increasing legitimate needs with decreasing available resources.

Since the 1980s, therefore, with the realization that funding provided by government alone could not adequately cater for the growing educational needs of a developing nation, "financial support from corporations and communities" became an important option, and the role of industry and the community in enhancing education generally became emphasized in Nigeria. In fact, the UNESCO has prescribed "the strengthening of university-industry partnerships so that with funds provided by industries, higher education institutions can carry out research and development functions for industries, with mutual benefits for both parties" (UNESCO, 1998).

The scope of the contributions of industry to enhancing engineering education in Nigeria extends over a wide range of relationships and functions. These will be considered under the following broad categories: financial contributions, contributions to students' informal training, contributions to post-graduation training, contributions to continuing professional development, and others.

Financial Contributions of Industry to Engineering Education

The contributions of corporations towards the financing of education in general in Nigeria have not yet been properly evaluated in quantitative terms. It will therefore understandably be difficult to evaluate them with specific reference to engineering education. For example, many large corporations have contributed to education in their operational communities either in cash or by building schools and supplying equipment, and this often without any systematic records being taken. Undoubtedly, engineering education, being an integral part of education in general, has benefited from such contributions. Moreover, with the emphasis and priority accorded by the national policy on education to scientific and technological education, coupled with the fact that these areas normally require more funding before their needs are satisfied compared to other areas of education, it is to be expected that engineering education would take a very large chunk of these contributions.

Under the financial contributions of industry to engineering education, we have:

1. Support for equipment acquisition

Engineering laboratory and research equipment are very costly and their acquisition is capital-intensive. With the fragile economic base of an undeveloped nation, and with so many essential social needs screaming for attention, the level of government funding of education is generally low. Understandably, therefore, many of the university engineering laboratories are poorly-equipped (in terms of the available equipment being inadequate or some of those available being obsolete and outdated). Certain corporate organizations and industrial concerns have risen up to this challenge by providing funds for engineering faculties to purchase laboratory and research equipment, purchasing and supplying the equipment directly to the faculties, and/or donating old equipment to be replaced by them to the faculties. Donations also often include computing equipment, engineering books, manuals and design handbooks.

2. Support through Provision of Research Grants

Another avenue of industry's support for engineering faculties is in the area of provision of funding for general research, in the research areas of interest of the engineering faculties. This support has to some extent arrested the "brain drain" phenomenon, which was already rising to alarming proportions. Under this programme, seasoned academics and researchers are empowered and enabled to initiate and engage in meaningful research. With this, instead of feeling that they are idly "wasting away", they are able to attain some fulfillment. They therefore remain within the developing nation's engineering faculties, instead of drifting away to environments with more research opportunities and more conducive to research as obtainable in overseas institutions. Also, with the availability of research grants and more research opportunities, indigenous academics and researchers already based in the more advanced countries are able to return to the country. However, the level of this type of support and funding is very low as Donwa ^[7] has discovered that Government support accounts for over 98% of research funding in Nigerian universities, while a major portion of the rest comes from foreign agencies with very little coming from industry. She suggested a more intensive approach towards the establishment of collaborative links between universities and industries, while industry involvement in funding should be seen as a corporate social responsibility.

3. Contract Research and Patronage of Consultancy Services

This entails funding of research activities of special interest and direct applicability in the specific industry. Much of industrial support to universities is provided through contracts for special projects. A good example of this is the various contracts for product development awarded to many engineering faculties by the Raw Materials Research and Development Council, and other bodies such as the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology and the Product Development Agency. Another area is the engagement of the faculties in consultancy services such as design and supervision of engineering projects. The engineering faculties and individual researchers through these means generate extra funds which can be further ploughed into other research activities. In general, the contracted agreements to a department or an individual investigator generate strong person-to-person interactions that favor technical cooperation which lasts for years.

Another important activity of industry in encouraging research activities in the universities is the organization and sponsorship of fairs and exhibitions of engineering research products and processes,

and the provision of outlets for research results through their adoption for further development and commercial application in industry.

4. Indirect Contributions through the Education Tax Fund

The Education Tax Fund (ETF) was set up in 1993 by law (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1993). The Fund was designed as an interventionist agency charged with restoring, rehabilitating and consolidating the education sector. Its board was inaugurated and charged with the responsibility of operating, managing and administering the fund.

Under the law, companies registered in the country are required to pay 2% of their assessable profit as a special education tax to accrue to the Fund. A substantial amount of money has been collected and administered under the Fund. For example, between 1994 and 1999, the Fund had collected and administered a total of 11.2 billion Nigerian naira (Daku, 2000). This amount translates to about only US\$80 million, but in the local currency it can achieve a lot. From 1999 to 2006, the Fund had administered a total sum of a little above 65.5 billion Nigerian naira, according to Table 1 in the appendix, compiled as a summary of the information on intervention funds allocated annually in those years by the Education Trust Fund to several areas of the Nigerian education sector, given by the Education Trust Fund (Daku, 2000).

Much of the Fund's intervention has been targeted directly at enhancing engineering education in the country, especially in the area of building of laboratories and provision of engineering laboratory equipment, provision of research grants, etc., while engineering education benefits from the Fund's other interventions indirectly as an integral part of education. Over the years, some of the contributions of the ETF have included:

- funding of capital projects on university campuses (provision of new and rehabilitation of old laboratory blocks, lecture halls, students' hostels, staff offices and equipment, road networks, transportation equipment such as buses, etc.)
- provision of infrastructure (electrification and alternative power generating facilities, potable water reticulation schemes and provision of boreholes for water supply from underground reservoirs, campus-based water treatment plants, health facilities, sporting and recreational facilities, etc.)
- purchase of laboratory equipment
- acquisition of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) equipment and facilities (e.g. internet connectivity, etc.)
- provision of research funds for academia, funding of conferences and sponsorship of academia to attend, etc.
- library acquisition of books and journals (the collection of certain libraries had become deplorable and outdated due to perpetual abysmally low budgetary allocations) and ICT equipment for computerization of library services

5. Financial Contributions to the Industrial Training Fund

The Industrial Training Fund (ITF) is the body that administers the Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), both of which will be considered in the next section. Under the law, funding of SIWES is partly paid for through contributions from employers. Employers are also mandated to provide welfare services for students on SIWES placement with them. Apart from these, some individual firms and industrial concerns optionally pay 'extra' allowances to the students on placement in their establishment.

6. Provision of Incentives to Engineering Students

A significant contribution of industry to engineering education is in the area of provision of scholarships, bursaries and awards for engineering students with outstanding academic performances as a way of encouraging students to study engineering.

Contributions to Students' Informal Training

Apart from the afore-mentioned financial contributions of industry to engineering education in Nigeria, industry plays an even more important role through its contributions to engineering students' informal training. Nigeria's philosophy for engineering education (National Universities Commission, 1989)

acknowledges that the complete engineering education of engineering personnel should extend beyond the formal training obtained in the universities to periods of tutelage in industrial environments. This is administered under the Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) programme. The informal portion of the engineer's training is done in close association with industries in the country.

The Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme gives students in higher institutions of learning the opportunity to explore the practical realities of their various fields of study by working in the field for specified periods of time during their training. The Scheme exposes students to industry-based skills necessary for a smooth transition from the classroom to the world of work after graduation. It affords them the opportunity of being exposed to the needed experience in handling machinery and equipment which are usually not available in the educational institutions.

In Nigeria, the SIWES is a major integral component of the engineering training of students. The National Universities Commission's Minimum Academic Standard for Engineering and Technology (National Universities Commission, 1989) recommends a minimum of six months of supervised training in industry. This period usually covers the whole of the second semester of the fourth year of a five-year degree programme and the adjoining three months summer holiday. The provision of space for attachment in this regard in industries is a major contribution of industry towards enhancing engineering education.

Charged with administering the SIWES is the Industrial Training Fund (ITF), set up in 1971 by an act (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1971). The ITF is charged with ensuring, amongst others, the provision and payment of allowances for students during their industrial training placements, the provision and payment of supervision allowances to the students' academic (university-based) and industry-based supervisors, as well as the general coordination and administration of the SIWES program (sourcing for places in industry and allocating them to the students, arranging for unannounced visits to the industries by the students' university-based supervisors, provision of required stationery for the reports of the students and their university-based and industry-based supervisors, etc.)

Under the ITF act, employers are mandated (i) To collaborate with the institutions in the preparation of job specifications for the approved courses for SIWES; (ii) To provide places for, and accept students for Industrial Attachment; (iii) To provide welfare services, e.g. medication and payment for hospitalization of students while on attachment whenever the need arises; (iv) To participate fully in the assessment of programmes/students by completing the necessary instrument, e.g. the assessment forms, the logbooks, etc.; (v) To allow students have access to their facilities; and (vi) To appoint an Industry-based Supervisor for students on attachment.

During their SIWES attachments, students are required to be exposed to different areas of training in the industrial setup and environment, as well as the colleagues in industry taking time and pain to take them through the rudiments of practical training. This of course calls for sacrifice of industrial concerns whose main preoccupation may be the full and optimal utilization of their time and resources in conducting their business. It is evident that without the cooperation of industry, this aspect of engineering education in Nigeria would be impossible.

The contributions of industry to SIWES go beyond the aforesaid. To finance the scheme, the ITF Act provides for subventions on the part of government, as well as for contributions on the part of employers. Apart from the financial contributions and the welfare services they are mandated to provide for students on industrial attachment, some individual firms and industrial concerns optionally pay 'extra' allowances to the students on placement in their establishment.

Apart from SIWES, another important area of industry's relevance in the training of engineering students is in making their facilities available for industrial visits and excursions. These visits are a major sacrifice on the part of industry in that they constitute a source of distraction from their primary area of operation (economic production). Apart from the time thus wasted, they have to ensure the safety and well-being of the students on industrial visit.

Contributions to Post-Graduation Pre-Registration Training

Under Nigerian law, only engineers that have attained chartered status are eligible to practice the engineering profession in the country. This is done by the prospective engineer fulfilling all necessary conditions for professional registration as stipulated by the regulatory body, the Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN) and having his name placed in its register of registered or chartered engineers.

After graduation from university, young personnel within the engineering profession desiring to be registered professionally must receive further post-graduate industrial training under the supervision of experienced engineers in industry for a pupillage period of at least two years before they can fully qualify for professional registration. The programme is designed as an essential component of the requirements for registration, and it is administered by the COREN under its Supervised Industrial Training Scheme In Engineering (SITSIE). At the end of the tutelage period of two or more years the trainee will have qualified to obtain from his employer a Certificate of Experience, necessary for registration, and he will be expected to have acquired enough skills and experience to enable him perform effectively in subsequent appointment.

While SIWES has been designed to cater for the industrial practical experience component of the trainee's academic programme, SITSIE has been designed to help provide the necessary post-qualification practical experience prior to professional registration.

Contributions to Continuing Engineering Education

The engineering profession is very dynamic. It changes in response to advances in science and as a result of changes in society. As people change their lifestyle and work patterns, the demand for new technologies increases. In the last ten years in particular, developments in information and communications technologies (ICT) have revolutionized the engineering profession both in its breadth and depth of application. New courses, new areas of specialization, different tools of design and analysis have appeared over the last few years (Antonio and Massaquoi, 2001). This rapid progress in engineering requires that an engineer becomes a continuous learner for as long as he remains in professional practice. He must take advantage of every reasonable opportunity available to him to ensure that he sustains, improves and develops his knowledge and professional competence. This is done through Continuing Engineering Education (CEE). Continuing Engineering Education (CEE) is therefore very important in that it offers an opportunity for practicing engineers to enhance their professional knowledge and remain in tune with changes in their profession. For sustainable development in a fledgling economy, the continuous updating on global changes in various aspects of one's profession is very essential.

In Nigeria, CEE is considered not only as a necessary requirement for keeping abreast with technological change, but also as a statutory obligation within the practice of the engineering profession in the country. Under Nigerian law the Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN) requires all engineers to keep abreast with current trends in the profession by attending relevant seminars, workshops, conferences, lectures, short-term and part-time refresher courses. These activities are allotted weightings, called Continuing Professional Development Units (CPDUs), and participation in such activities earns an engineer CPDUs. The regulations stipulate that for any engineering practitioner to be eligible to continue to be on the register of COREN, he or she must accumulate a minimum of 20 CPDUs annually (Antonio and Massaquoi, 2001). A defaulting engineer would have his or her name removed from the Register, and it is illegal for any person whose name has been so removed to practice as an engineer for the duration of the period of such removal. The employer of such a person is also liable to penalty. These requirements are effectively met through membership of COREN-recognised professional associations and societies. Under CEE, an engineer is also expected to subscribe to reputable engineering journals, and find ways and means of receiving and studying current journals, magazines, catalogues, books, and other literature on modern technology.

The employers have a major role to play in this aspect of the engineer's education. In principle, they must give staff development and training grants to the engineer employee whenever he requests for them; they must grant permission for study leave for specialist postgraduate courses; they must subscribe to engineering journals as well as make provisions to receive other publications to avail their employees the opportunity of studying them and keeping in touch with modern trends; they must not

hinder their employees from fraternizing with members, or participating in the activities, of their professional associations and societies; etc. All the foregoing require some degree of sacrifice.

CONCLUSION

The contributions of industry to university engineering education in Nigeria take the form of financial contributions in the provision of equipment and infrastructure, financial contributions toward research and the other forms of encouraging research, and its involvement in the informal training of the engineering students, and in the training of the young graduate before his professional registration, as well as in the continuing engineering education of engineering practitioners within industry. Okojie (2007) has highlighted the contributions of industry in University-Industry partnerships in Nigeria to include (i) provision of social infrastructural within the universities, (ii) commissioning and funding of specific research projects in Nigerian Universities to enhance the development of their products and services, (iii) partnering with the universities for graduate retraining and quality enhancement, and (iv) allowing academics into the industry on specific projects for knowledge exchange. He suggested that the universities could facilitate this partnership through (i) focusing on demand-driven research and development to attract patronage by the industry and government, (ii) ensuring capacity building programmes which would further scholarship and be of relevance in the economy, (iii) collaborating in manpower planning with inputs from the industry in curriculum reviews, and (iv) developing expertise and alliances in specific areas through collaboration with other institutions. He stated the benefits of such partnership to include (i) a multi-faceted synergy of access to expertise, working culture, funding and industry knowledge, (ii) a proven means of driving technological innovation, economic growth and industrial development, (iii) available government grants for Research and Development being channeled mainly to basic/developmental research, (iv) the industry partner becomes more competitive by reducing overheads through outsourcing Research and Development to Universities, (v) an integrated and directional guide to Research and Development efforts by the government and industry partners, and (vi) students develop leadership and team skills as they benefit from real-life experiences not available in the classroom.

In the area of research, the traditional relationships between universities and industry obtainable in the advanced countries are not so well-developed in Nigeria. The research linkage area of cooperation between universities and industries alone have been further categorized (Peters *et al*, 1982) into six major sub-categories, namely: (i) General Support; (ii) Contract Research; (iii) Research Centers and Institutes; (iv) Research Consortia; (v) Industrial Associate/ Affiliate Programs; and (vi) New Business Incubators and Research Parks

It is only the first two categories that are commonly available in Nigeria, and these have been treated above. (i) General Support continues to be an integral part of industrial philanthropy and takes the form of monetary gifts and/or equipment donations for teaching and research purposes. (ii) Contract Research involves the provision of industrial support to universities through contracts for special projects.

Because of the low-technology-driven economy of the country, the other four categories involving joint research partnerships, as described (Peters *et al*, 1982), are not so well-established. (iii) Research Centers and Institutes focusing on a certain technology are established by universities in order to facilitate the procedures of contracting and communicating between researchers and industry, such centers often providing the environment for the cross-disciplinary approach that industrial problems often require. (iv) Research Consortia can be characterized as specific mission programs organized to ensure that generic or mission-oriented research will be carried out by one or more universities. Typically, participating companies pay a membership fee; the university offers laboratory space and graduate students and faculty researchers. (v) Industrial Associate/Affiliate Programs are set up by many research universities to provide member firms with access to campus research and resources. (vi) Business Incubators and Research Parks are located on or near the campus and are intended to draw technology-intensive firms into the university environment.

While these types of research relationships may not be available in Nigeria, the other areas of industry's contributions to engineering education in Nigeria in terms of contributions to informal engineering training and financing could find applicability in other countries. For example, the notion of an Education Tax Fund as practiced in Nigeria has been suggested for implementation in other

African countries to tackle the perennial problem of inadequate educational funding (Antonio and Massaquoi, 2001).

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APPENDIX

Table 1: GENERAL ANALYSIS AND SUMMARY OF ETF ALLOCATIONS TO INSTITUTIONS (1999 - 2006)

YEAR	UNIVERSITIES	POLYTECHNICS	COLLEGES OF EDUCATION	MONOTECHNICS	SECONDARY SCHOOLS	PRIMARY EDUCATION	SPECIAL PROJECTS	TOTAL
1999	2,124,999,960.12	1,087,209,288.00	1,099,137,930.00	0.00	675,000,000.00	3,132,000,000.00	0.00	8,118,347,178.12
2000	1,050,000,000.00	450,000,000.00	520,000,000.00	230,000,000.00	781,800,001.75	1,117,199,997.90	248,035,944.18	4,397,035,943.83
2001	1,794,128,000.00	967,500,000.00	1,116,069,500.00	345,000,000.00	1,587,750,000.00	2,167,200,000.00	0.00	7,977,647,500.00
2002	3,243,500,000.00	1,642,500,000.00	1,742,625,000.00	448,000,000.00	2,792,750,000.00	2,709,000,000.00	0.00	12,578,375,000.00
2003	1,440,500,000.00	634,500,000.00	678,625,000.00	290,000,000.00	1,003,750,000.00	1,548,000,000.00	520,000,000.00	6,115,375,000.00
2004	1,515,750,000.00	722,750,000.00	739,625,000.00	285,000,000.00	803,000,000.00	1,855,260,000.00	65,000,000.00	5,986,385,000.00
2005	2,025,000,000.00	1,657,500,000.00	1,259,000,000.00	348,000,000.00	2,410,571,428.00	2,474,460,000.00	10,000,000.00	10,184,531,428.00
2006	2,130,000,000.00	1,122,000,000.00	1,240,000,000.00	649,000,000.00	806,650,000.00	4,199,805,000.00	0.00	10,147,455,000.00
TOTAL	15,323,877,960.12	8,283,959,288.00	8,395,082,430.00	2,595,000,000.00	10,861,271,429.75	19,202,924,997.90	843,035,944.18	65,505,152,049.95